

Reduction of Copper(II)-Triglycine (1 : 1) System at Dropping Mercury Electrode : Large Difference in Redox Behaviour of Copper(II) for O-Bonded and N⁻-Bonded Peptide Group

H. L. NIGAM*, KRISHNA B. PANDEYA and RAM N. PATEL

Department of Chemistry, A. P. S. University, Rewa-486 003

Manuscript received 14 September 1992

Complex formation between copper(II) and triglycine has been studied polarographically in aqueous sodium perchlorate medium. The results have been interpreted in terms of various species suggested by Martell *et al.*¹ and Sarkar *et al.*² Present findings favour the structures suggested by Sarkar *et al.*². It has also been concluded that even in the physiological pH-range the species may undergo bonding site interconversion causing large changes in the redox property of copper. This may offer an explanation to the considerable variability in redox behaviour of type-2 copper in copper proteins

Copper is an important trace metal. Copper-containing enzymes and proteins are widely distributed in both animals and plants¹. They are known to perform two main functions, namely, (i) electron transport and (ii) dioxygen transport and metabolism. There has been a continued effort to mimic the structure and functions of the metalloproteins in the simple low molecular weight metal complexes. Type-2 copper sites, show optical and epr spectra similar to those of simple square-planar copper(II) complexes. In particular, copper(II) chelates of amino acids and peptides are used as models for type-2 copper centres in copper proteins. Type-2 copper sites show considerable variability in redox behaviour. In this context it would be gratifying to learn that the copper(II)-GGGH₃ (triglycine) system shows a large change in the half-wave potential for reduction at d.m.e. on intramolecular rearrangement by way of change in donor atom, as concluded in the present study. This makes a stronger case for use of copper(II)-peptide complexes as models for type-2 sites in copper proteins.

Triglycine is a simple peptide with two peptide bonds. It has four potential coordination sites, viz. an amino group, a carboxylic group and two peptide groups. Further, the two peptide groups can act as a O or N⁻ donor under different experimental conditions. Formation of complex of triglycine with copper(II) was first studied potentiometrically by Martell and Kim³. Subsequently several workers have studied ternary complexes of copper(II) with triglycine and glycine^{3,4}, ethylenediamine⁵, bipyridyl^{6,6} and imidazoles⁷.

In the present communication we report the polarographic reduction (at d.m.e.) of copper(II)-GGGH₃ (1 : 1) system. A look at the half-wave potentials for the reduction of various species formed, reveals that the change in the coordinations site of the peptide group from O to N⁻ causes a large negative shift in the E_{1/2} value. Polarographic

reduction (at d.m.e.) of the copper(II)-GGH₂ (1 : 1) system was reported recently by our school⁸.

Results and Discussion

The polarograms are shown in Fig. 1. In each case the reduction waves are diffusion-controlled. The half-wave potentials have been listed in Table I. The reduction of copper(II) yielded diffusion current

TABLE I—HALF-WAVE POTENTIALS (NEGATIVE, IN V VS S.C.E.) FOR COPPER(II)-GGGH₃ (1 : 1)

pH	Wave 1	Wave 2	Wave 3
4.00	0.010		
4.53	0.009	0.326	
5.00	0.010	0.320	
5.58	0.013	0.270	0.760
6.00	0.019	0.246	0.735
6.75	0.02	0.250	0.680
7.15	—	0.235	0.645
8.54	—	—	0.650
9.00	—	—	0.590
10.00	—	—	0.625
10.55	—	—	0.650
11.55	—	—	0.675

of the magnitude lying in the range for the two-electron reduction. The plots of E_{a.e.} vs log i/(i_{a-i}) were virtually nonlinear. The problem of nonlinearity in the conventional log plots caused by irreversibility has been resolved by Oldham and Parry⁹. According to these authors the equation for an irreversible diffusion-controlled wave at 25° is given by

$$-E_{a.e.} = -E_{1/2} + (0.059/n) \log[x(5.5-x)/5(1-x)]$$

where, $x = i_E/i_{1tm}$, i_E is current at potential E . The plots of E_{a.e.} vs log[x(5.5-x)/5(1-x)] yield straight lines with slopes of 0.059/n and intercept of -E_{1/2}.

Fig. 1. Polarograms of Cu^{2+} -GGGH₃ (1 : 1) at different pH values.

Martell and Kim² studied complex formation between copper(II) and GGGH₃ potentiometrically and suggested the formation of four complex species. Sarkar and Lau³ also studied complex formation between copper(II) and GGGH₃ potentiometrically and suggested formation of four complex species. However, the structures suggested by the two

groups for the four complex species are slightly different, as regards the binding sites in the ligand. The two sets of the suggested structures are given in Table 2 for the sake of ready comparison. Also the percentage distribution of various species at different pH-values as evaluated by Martell and Kim² is given in Fig. 2.

TABLE 2—STRUCTURES SUGGESTED BY TWO SCHOOLS FOR VARIOUS SPECIES WITH COPPER(II)-GGGH₃ (1 : 1) SYSTEM

Species	Sarkar's structure*	Martell's structure**
1		
2		
3		
4		

*Ref. 3. **Ref. 2.

Fig. 2. Distribution of various species at different pH values.

Starting with pH 4.0 we have recorded the polarograms for the copper(II)-GGGH₃ system at different pH-values. At pH=4, the polarogram shows only one wave. The second wave appears at pH 4.5. While the first wave continuously loses height with increase in pH and ceases to exist above pH 6.75, the second wave first gains height, reaches maximum height at pH ~6.0 and then loses height. This wave too ceases at pH~8.5. The pH-profile of the wave-height of wave 2 is quite

similar to the pH-profile of the abundance (percentage) of the species 2 (Fig. 3). Wave 2 is, therefore, evidently associated with species 2. Also the pH-profile of the height of wave 1 parallels the pH-profile of the total abundance (percentage) of Cu²⁺ aq and the species 1 (Fig. 3). Wave 1 thus represents simultaneous reduction of Cu²⁺ aq and species 1. The half-wave potential for this wave lies in the range -0.01 to -0.02 V, which is quite close to the half-wave potential for the reduction of Cu²⁺ aq. Under our experimental conditions, the half-wave potential of Cu²⁺ aq has been obtained at -0.01 V (Fig. 4). It appears, therefore, that the species 1 is a weakly coordinated species, which has a half-wave potential quite close to that of Cu²⁺ aq. A third wave comes into existence at pH ≤5.5. Martell's distribution curve also shows birth of species 3 at around this pH, whose percentage abundance continuously increases and reaches 100% at pH 8.5. Thus, the wave 3 may be assigned to the species 3. The pH-profile of the height of this wave shows a continuous increase with pH and reaches a constant maximum value at pH ~8.5 (Fig. 3). At pH 8.5, species 3 is in 100% abundance, so that the polarographic wave obtained at this pH is characteristic of species 3. The wave is diffusion-controlled. It has half-wave potential of -0.65 V and diffusion current of 7.28 μA. Also, the wave is irreversible for two-electron reduction at d.m.e. (slope, 0.22 V).

Beyond pH 8.5, species 3 starts converting into species 4. With increase in pH, population of species 4 continuously increases at the cost of species 3. Total concentration of species 3 and 4 is throughout constant at 100%. However, throughout this pH-range only one polarographic wave is obtained. Obviously, this wave represents simultaneous reduction of both the species, 3 and 4. Also, the height of this wave remains constant throughout, corresponding to the constant total abundance of the two species.

The half-wave potential of wave 1 shifts to slightly more negative value with increase in pH. This may be due to the equilibrium Cu²⁺ aq ⇌ 1, that obviously shows rightward shift with increase in pH. With increase in pH, E_{1/2} of wave 2 records a small shift towards less negative value up to pH 7.0. This observation suggests that the equilibrium 1 ⇌ 2 is rate-determining step in reduction of species 2. E_{1/2} of wave 3 records a small shift towards less negative value upto pH 8.5. This again means that the equilibrium 2 ⇌ 3 is rate-determining step in the reduction of species 3. Beyond pH 8.5, the E_{1/2} of this wave shows a shift to more negative value with increase in pH. This is because of the rightward shift of the equilibrium 2 ⇌ 3. Species 4 obtained from deprotonation of 3, should certainly have more negative E_{1/2}.

Various equilibria, considered in the metal-ligand system under discussion, are Cu²⁺ aq ⇌ 1 ⇌ 2 ⇌ 3 ⇌ 4. Since Cu²⁺ aq and 1 are found to undergo simultaneous reduction, this equilibrium (Cu²⁺

Fig. 3. pH-dependence of wave heights and percentage abundance of various species.

$\text{aq} \rightleftharpoons 1$) is faster than the polarographic time-scale. Similarly, equilibrium $3 \rightleftharpoons 4$ is also faster than the polarographic time scale, so that 3 and 4 reduce simultaneously. Considerable difference in the half-wave potentials for the reduction of 1 and 2 and those of 2 and 3 suggests that equilibria $1 \rightleftharpoons 2$ and $2 \rightleftharpoons 3$ are much slower than the polarographic time-scale.

As concluded earlier on the basis of simultaneous reduction of $\text{Cu}^{2+} \text{ aq}$ and 1. 1 should be a very weakly coordinated species. Martell's structure for 1 contains three chelate rings (donor groups NH_2 , 2NH and COO^-) and as such does not meet this criterion. It is unlikely that a species with three chelate rings as described above gives $\text{Cu}^{2+} \text{ aq} \rightleftharpoons 1$ equilibrium faster than polarographic time-scale

Fig. 4. Polarogram of Cu^{2+} aq $[\text{CuClO}_4]_0 = 1 \text{ mM}$, $[\text{NaClO}_4] = 0.1 \text{ M}$.

and may reduce at the same half-wave potential (or very close to it) as does Cu^{2+} aq. Structure suggested by Sarkar and Lau³ for 1, also consisting of one chelate ring (donor groups NH_2 , $\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), may also not meet the above requirements. We again prefer to suggest that species 1 is a very weakly coordinated species (formed probably with monodentate peptide bonded through COO^- only and with three water molecules). Further, large difference in the $E_{1/2}$ values of the waves 2 and 3 call for a severe change in the coordination spheres of Cu^{II} in species 2 and 3. Again Martell's structures for these species do not meet this requirement. His structures contain NNNO coordination for both 2 and 3. Sarkar's structure, on the other

hand, provides $\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{Cu}^{2+} \begin{matrix} \diagup \text{N} \\ \diagdown \text{N} \\ \diagdown \text{O} \end{matrix}$ structure for 2 and

$\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{Cu}^{2+} \begin{matrix} \diagup \text{N} \\ \diagdown \text{N} \\ \diagdown \text{N} \end{matrix}$ for 3. Change from 3 to 4 in Martell's structure requires a stereochemical change

from four-coordinate nearly square-planar to five-coordinate distorted square-pyramidal. This less well accounts for the polarographic observation of simultaneous reduction of the species 3 and 4. Sarkar's structures on the other hand involve no structural change in going from 3 to 4. It instead involves only deprotonation of the coordinated water molecule,

About the species at physiological pH: In the system being studied Cu^{2+} aq and species 1 are non-existent at the physiological pH, so that the species present are 2 and 3 only. At this pH (7.15) species 2 has a half-wave potential of -0.235 V and species 3 of -0.645 V . Species 3 is formed from species 2 by change in a coordinating site of the peptide from O (of $\text{C}=\text{O}$) to N^- . Since the two species are in equilibrium in the physiological pH-range, it is possible that such coordination position changes occur in vivo in the copper proteins to make possible the manipulation in the redox behaviour of copper. This also explains the considerable variability in the redox behaviour of the type-2 copper in the copper proteins. Such change in the redox behaviour of copper in copper-peptide systems has earlier been observed by Margerum *et al.*¹⁰ in their studies on redox potential of copper(III)-copper(II). They concluded that the deprotonated peptide nitrogen is a strong σ -donor which helps to stabilise the higher oxidation state of copper. That is, $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ reduction should become more difficult and, therefore, $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ reduction half-wave potential should become more negative. The relative effectiveness of donor groups in stabilising higher oxidation state is: peptide $\text{N}^- > \text{NH}_2 > \text{OH}^- > \text{COO}^- > \text{imidazole}$.

Experimental

The stock solution of the metal ion was prepared by dissolving copper(II) perchlorate hexahydrate (Aldrich) in double-distilled water. The solutions of triglycine (Sigma) was also prepared in double-distilled water. Analytical grade sodium perchlorate (E. Merck) was used for preparing supporting electrolyte solution. Triton X-100 (Rhom and Hoas Company) was used as maximum suppressor.

Polarograms were recorded with a Systronics 1632 polarograph in conjunction with a Systronics 1501 recorder with a three-electrode set-up. The capillary used were of following characteristics at open circuit at room temperature (25°): $h=50 \text{ cm}$, $m=2.5 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t=1.6 \text{ s}$. The pH measurements were made with a Control Dynamics pH-meter (accuracy $\pm 0.01 \text{ pH unit}$).

Polarograms were recorded for the system $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} : \text{GGGH}_3 :: 1 : 1$ in the pH range 4.00–11.55. The cell solution was deaerated by purging pure nitro-

gen. In each system, pH was maintained using dilute solutions of NaOH and HClO₄.

Acknowledgement

This work was done under the financial assistance from C.S.I.R., New Delhi.

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